

Project Description – Project Proposals in the Area of Scientific Library Services and Information Systems (LIS)

LIS Funding Programme or Call:

The Age of Replications: Establishing a Multidisciplinary Diamond Open Access Infrastructure and Community Portal

Setting the Stage for the Age of Replications Lukas Röseler, Münster

Project Description

1 Starting Point

State of the art and preliminary work

Innovation versus Robustness

Scientific research is currently undergoing a shift from a sole focus on innovation toward an emphasis on robustness, reliability, and repeatability. Numerous fields have committed to increasing the number of replications following findings that replications are rare, and if done, often fail to substantiate earlier claims (e.g., Aczel et al., 2026; Ankel-Peters et al., 2023; Camerer et al., 2018; Makel et al., 2016; Open Science Collaboration, 2015). Fast research progress and excellent research is not possible if a lack of repeatability prevents genuine advancement (c.f., the collapse of decades of behavioral priming research in psychology, Doyen et al., 2012). Consequently, repeatability in the form of computational reproducibility (same data, same code), recreate reproducibility (same data, new code), direct replicability (different data, similar method), and conceptual replicability (different data, different method, same question), needs to underpin trustworthy, generalizable, and applicable research. This presupposes open access, open data and transparent discussions regarding generalizability. Academic societies, funders, and researchers are increasingly recognizing the importance of repeatability, leading to widespread calls for replications, the creation of replication databases, tools to increase visibility, and methodological advances. At the same time, in comparison with other open science practices, replications are relatively rare even at the epicenter of the replication crisis (i.e., Social Psychology; Glöckner et al., 2024). Alongside these strong developments toward robustness is a necessary push for independence from for-profit publishers, who have not taken their responsibility for quality assurance seriously (Reed et al., 2026). Our diamond open access journal, *Replication Research (R2)*, responds to these two developments. It embodies the core values of good scientific practices, treats research as a public good, and approaches repeatability as a property that must be carefully established rather than blindly assumed. It takes the responsibility to publish high-quality reproductions and replications. R2 was developed by a community of 50 researchers and in the first six months after its launch in October 2025, we have received submissions from motivational psychology, stylometry, sociology, clinical psychology, and biology, a draft for a guest editorial by leaders of multiple large-scale replication projects, and we have formed partnerships with world-leading initiatives such as the Center for Open Science (COS), Institute for Replication, Collaborative Replication and Education Project (CREP), and more.

Challenges

Researchers who wish to step up to the repeatability challenge still face a lack of guidance and best practices concerning replication methods in numerous fields (e.g., Brandt et al., 2014;

Lakens, 2026). Furthermore, an overly polite culture of criticism or an overly combative culture of criticism can prevent constructive attempts to repeat research; because criticism is often taken personally, researchers tend to invent pseudo-innovative theories rather than working on existing ones collaboratively and impersonally. Formal criteria for research evaluation also hinder repeatability research in multiple ways, making it difficult for early career researchers to engage in this growing field. Together, these criteria perpetuate a bad image of replications, overemphasize innovative research questions, and ignore replication studies, which typically receive less attention (e.g., in the form of low citations; Hardwicke et al., 2021). This dynamic strengthens publisher lock-in (Brembs et al., 2023) by incentivizing publications in high-impact journals (Bakker et al., 2012). In turn, these high-impact journals remain disinterested in publishing individual replication reports because they are not highly cited. Large-scale replication studies (e.g., Open Science Collaboration, 2015) are an exception to this, but rarely report results for individual studies transparently and thus do not directly contribute to cumulative knowledge development.

Uniting the International and Multidisciplinary Community

The *Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training's* (FORRT) *Replication Hub*, led by Lukas Röseler, Lukas Wallrich, and Flavio Azevedo, has begun to address several of these challenges thanks to a strong community of over 260 contributors. The collaboration started with the FORRT Replications and Reversals resource, which crowdsourced details on over 600 scientific phenomena (“effects”) from 22 disciplines (Hartmann et al., 2026; <https://forrt.org/reversals>). Over time, this evolved into the FORRT Replication Database (Röseler et al., 2024), which is among one of the highest impact dataset publications in psychology (>24K views according to the journal’s website and >30K downloads according to the OSF, <https://osf.io/9r62x/files/osfstorage>; both accessed on 3/30/2026). During a partnership with the Center for Open Science, we have expanded the database from a crowdsourced to a double-coded and validated version (FReD 2.0) with 1,000 entries including effect sizes, sample sizes, and many more variables (<https://www.cos.io/blog/cos-and-forrt-partner-to-increase-discoverability-and-usability-of-replication-evidence>). To allow expansion beyond social sciences to humanities and natural sciences, we have are currently focusing on the FORRT Library of Reproduction and Replication Attempts (FLoRA; <https://github.com/forrtproject/FReD-data>) as a register of original and replication studies and the replication authors’ outcome judgment (2,167 pairs of studies as of 4/29/2026). The databases are complemented with accessibility tools such as an interactive dashboard (<https://forrt.org/explorer/>), an Annotator to check reference lists for replications (<https://forrt.org/annotator/>), a Zotero plug-in (Wallrich, Tondlekar, et al., 2026), an in-development Chromium plug-in, a serious research game “Guess the Replication” (Röseler & Röseler, 2026) for educational purposes where players have to predict replication outcomes based on the original study’s abstract, and numerous other applications that allow researchers to incorporate replications into their workflow. Experts from this community have developed a free *Handbook for Reproduction and Replication Studies* (Röseler, Wallrich, et al., 2025) and we have fostered partnerships with all major international actors in the area of replication research. For example, for the 2026 Love Replications Week (<https://forrt.org/LoveReplicationsWeek>), we collaborated with COS, other diamond open access journals (e.g., the Journal of Comments and Replications in Economics, JCRE), data repository holders (e.g., [TROLLing](https://trolling.org)), and reproducibility initiatives (e.g., German Reproducibility Network, Institute for Replication, CODECHECK) to gather 17 experts and 162 attendants

across 14 online talks, workshops, and discussions. Furthermore, we run projects to monitor and enhance the visibility of replications alongside meta-science research on predictors of replicability and citations of replications (e.g., a [preprint notifier](#)). These were developed during hackathons with research assistants and volunteers (e.g., [fall](#) and [spring](#) hackathons).

A community-owned journal as the tip of the replication iceberg

Demonstrating our strict commitment to reforming research assessment, I have officially signed the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (SF DORA) in my capacity as Editor-in-Chief of R2. Furthermore, our advocacy extends beyond the journal to the institutional level: I recently spearheaded the successful initiative that led the University of Münster to officially adopt both SF DORA and the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information, cementing the university's and our project's alignment with global open science standards (<https://www.uni-muenster.de/news/view.php?cmdid=15286&lang=en>). With the FORRT Replication Hub, we have gathered a multidisciplinary community of researchers that value replications and join us in our mission to have them become a natural part of every day research. Together, we have been coordinating and collaborating with replication initiatives around the globe. To complete the journey from finding, tracking, and conducting replications, we have decided to create a journal hosted by FORRT and the Münster Center for Open Science (MüCOS): *Replication Research* (R2). Publications are academic currency and key for research visibility, and with R2, we can publish high-quality replications and reproductions and support interdisciplinary exchange in the creation of methods (e.g., target selection, success definitions). R2 was created in an inclusive and collaborative way (Röseler, Wallrich, Adler, et al., 2025) where interested researchers could join us in an online discussion series ("Road to R2"), a hybrid symposium (Röseler, Moser, et al., 2025), and an open community call to comment on our journal descriptions and constitution. All materials are openly licensed and made publicly available (e.g., manuscript layouts for LaTeX, Word, and Google Docs, initial editorial assessment form, the constitution, and in the future review reports and reproducibility certificates; <https://zenodo.org/communities/r2/records>). Hosted by the University of Münster using the open-source *Open Journal System*, the journal's editorial board and advisory board are made up of renowned international experts, offering an unprecedented level of transparency and quality control for reproduction and replication studies. In April 2026, we initiated the foundation of the Replication Journal Federation, which is a network of replication journals for mutual support, workshops, coordination, projects and advocacy.

Differentiation from the National Service Centre for Diamond Open Access

While the National Service Centre for Diamond Open Access (SeDOA) provides vital foundational services for journal hosting and general open access transitions, the objectives of this project extend far beyond standard publishing workflows. The specific infrastructural needs of the replication community, such as the discipline-specific capacity building (WP1), the specialized meta-scientific policy interventions (WP2), and the highly customized development of the "ReplicateThis" nominations portal and CODECHECK integrations (WP3 & WP4), require dedicated, field-specific meta-science and software engineering expertise. While we will coordinate with the SeDOA's group that is concerned with XML publishing, the SeDOA's general portfolio cannot fulfill these highly specialized project goals. Therefore, additional DFG funding is required to build this targeted meta-scientific infrastructure, which will ultimately serve as a highly interoperable complement to the broader national Diamond OA ecosystem.

Analysis of Competition and Supply Gaps

The FORRT Library of Reproduction and Replication Attempts and its predecessor the FORRT Replication Database have been allowing us a comprehensive analysis of the replication publishing environment since they are the largest replication databases (e.g., via exploring journals that publish replications and journals that publish target studies; <https://forrt.org/journalranking/>). While several excellent platforms exist that publish replications (e.g., Meta-Psychology [MP], Journal of Comments and Replications in Economics [JCRE], ReScience C [RC], Rescience X [RX], Journal of Robustness Reports [JRR], Journal of Open Psychology Data [JOPD]), they are strictly discipline-bound (MP, JCRE, JOPD) or focus on a subset of re-doing research (e.g., RC focuses on computational research, JRR focuses on re-analyses of “high impact findings” by at least two researchers). Conversely, larger journals (e.g., PLOS ONE, Royal Society Open Science) accept replications but lack standardized reproducibility checks, a dedicated community framework, and other facets supporting openness (e.g., social responsibility review, lay summaries). Replication Research (R2) closes this critical supply gap by providing a multidisciplinary, Diamond OA journal exclusively dedicated to reproduction and replication studies and coordinating with open replication journals such as JCRE. By standardizing workflows across disciplines via the Replication Journal Federation, R2 minimizes competition with existing field-specific replication journals (e.g., R2 does not accept economics and forwards potential submissions to JCRE), engages in coordination to allow for the pooling resources (e.g., reproducibility checkers via the CODECHECK community) and standardizes best practices that can be adopted by the broader scientific community.

Moreover, we are aware of plans by a major commercial publisher, a research agency, and the Perspective on Scientific Error working group to create journals for replications. With the Replication Journal Federation, we are both in a position to coordinate with complementary efforts (e.g., a potential diamond OA journal that publishes computational reproductions or findings of errors in published articles - something that would not meet the scope of R2) and to compete with potential journals from well-funded publishers that require article processing charges.

Long-Term Sustainability

A critical prerequisite for any infrastructural project is its technical and operational viability beyond the initial funding period. Having operated the FORRT Replication Database for over four years with almost no dedicated funding and committing to a DOAJ indexing of R2 by early 2028 (Röseler, Wallrich, & Azevedo, 2025) and the FORRT community for over eight years, the long-term sustainability of *Replication Research* and the broader Replication Journal Federation (RJF) ecosystem is already structurally and financially secured, ensuring that the infrastructure will thrive after the DFG funding period has ended in Year 4 and beyond.

Technically, the journal is securely embedded within the institutional infrastructure of the University of Münster, which administers journals that are hosted by its partner the Hochschulbibliothekszenrum (HBZ) to provide a robust, permanent environment for academic journals using the Open Journal Systems (OJS). This guarantees continuous server maintenance, updates, and automated archiving on-site and via the PKN Preservation Network. Operationally, the Münster Center for Open Science (MüCOS) in cooperation with the Backlab at the department for psychology provides a permanent 50% FTE position dedicated to

operating the journal and managing editorial workflows. Consequently, the core publishing infrastructure is backed by solid institutional baseline funding. The *ReplicateThis* portal developed in this project will similarly be transitioned into this secure university environment.

Furthermore, the human infrastructure driving this project is highly resilient. We are currently experiencing an influx of community engagement. So far, we have received inquiries from over 35 volunteers wanting to join the editorial team as reviewers, reproducibility checkers, and associate editors, so that we currently have to decline offers for help, as our structural resources are fully saturated and our primary focus is now on processing incoming submissions. In November 2025, the first submission was made; in February and March 2026, we have received two submissions per month in April, we have received three and in May one submission (9 in total, which is more than our sister journals have received in 2026 so far). Our current resources permit handling about six to ten new manuscripts per month.

Ultimately, the requested DFG LIS funds are not intended to keep the journal alive, but rather to act as a catalyst. The grant will finance the technical development of the *ReplicateThis* portal, the initial capacity-building workshops, and the vital policy-intervention work. Once these ecosystems are built and interconnected, the automated technical pipelines, the guaranteed HBZ hosting, the MÜCOS personnel commitment, and the continuously replenishing volunteer base of the RJF will guarantee a fully self-sustaining diamond open access infrastructure for years to come.

FORRT, one of the R2 owners, including its Replication Hub, in which Replication Research, the Replication Journal Federation, FLoRA and many more projects are embedded, has been endorsed as a Programme of the the International Decade of Sciences for Sustainable Development, led by UNESCO and the United Nation due to its essential contribution to the UN's strategy (<https://forrt.org/educators-corner/023-forward-a-unesco-decade-of-science-programme/>). With a strong backing and a considerable proportion of infrastructure in place, we are now preparing the next phase, which will consist of support for replications at a deeper level than before: Beyond enabling early-adopters of replications to engage in this research practice, we will change systemic barriers such as the culture of criticism and institutional guidelines that hinder replication attempts. This will lead to a long-term position of *Replication Research* not only as a service to *early adopters* of replications but the *larger research community*.

2 Objectives and work programme

Anticipated total duration of the project

The anticipated total duration of the project is 36 months.

Objectives

The overarching goal of this project is to exert a sustainable and positive impact on the culture of replication research, paving the way for a long-term increase in the recognition of such research within the broader academic community. Specifically, we aim to further establish and foster the unique position of our diamond open access journal, Replication Research. To achieve this overarching goal, we pursue a set of specific and measurable project objectives for the 36-month funding period: (1) expansion to further fields via the removal of discipline-specific barriers by training early career researchers and publishing a field-specific replication handbook, (2) removal of institutional barriers by analyzing U15/Russell Group regulations and delivering tailored, replication-friendly policy templates for decision-makers, (3) increase of efficiency by integrating shared XML publishing and CODECHECK reproducibility workflows across other replication journals, and (4) removal of cultural barriers via the launch and algorithmic seeding of a replication nomination portal to systematically crowdsource replication targets.

Removing the Barrier of Expertise: Provision of Field-Specific Guidance

A large proportion of replications has been done in psychology, economics, education, business, and sociology (Tyner et al., 2026), though issues of replicability and reproducibility are not restrained to these fields. We will provide field-specific guidance for replications in disciplines where such practices are currently underrepresented but clearly feasible, namely Linguistics, Marketing, and Neuroscience. This effort will be facilitated by members of R2 editorial team with whom we will cooperate on this proposal and who possess expertise in replication or reproduction studies and their respective disciplines. The primary outputs for this objective will include targeted workshops and the publication of deep-dive chapters in a dedicated, openly accessible book (WIP version available at https://forrt.org/replication_handbook).

Removing the Barrier of Research Assessment: Revision of Promotional Guidelines and Policy Briefs

Researchers are guided by how they are evaluated. A side effect of promotional guidelines and their alignment with high-impact publication outlets has been the penalizing of replications. For example, some PhD programs require publication of original research and systematically devalue replications. We aim to structurally improve research evaluation by developing recommendations for academic societies and institutions on how to evaluate replications. With FLoRA, we are already tracking replication rates in the aforementioned fields, which we will use to provide detailed breakdowns of their respective replication cultures and best practices. By systematically reviewing current promotional guidelines for criteria that impede diamond open access publishing and repeatability research from universities in Germany and the United Kingdom (two countries with whose communities we are closely linked, allowing us to build upon recent institutional assessment data gathered by the UKRN-led OR4 project), we will actively nudge committees, institutions, and societies to update their guidelines in accordance with field-specific best practices laid out in our policy brief and to formally position themselves regarding the value of individual replication studies.

Removing the Barrier of Resources: Expansion of the Replication Journal Federation

Maintaining a journal independent of a publisher can pose several additional challenges: Services for copy-editing, reviewer databases, and reproducibility checking all have to be built from scratch. To make use of the scalability of these editorial activities, we will develop decentralized services. For this, we will leverage the "Replication Journal Federation" ([RJF](#)), a network of replication journals that we recently founded. At the RJF, we are already providing structural guidance for other journals like our partner journals JCRE, JOPD, and the Rescience journals have done for us, such as indexing support. During the project, we will collaboratively create a standardized reviewer Code of Conduct for replications and reproductions that pays special attention to criticism of researchers versus criticism of research. Moreover, we have been pooling resources for joint advertisement and replication workshops and will expand these to a shared pool of reproducibility checkers, copy-editors, and shared workflows for generating machine-readable full texts (JATS XML/HTML) to comply with cOAlition S requirements across all federation journals.

Removing the Barrier of Research Culture: Implementation of the "ReplicateThis" Portal

Embedded within the RJF, we will launch "ReplicateThis," a dedicated replication nominations portal (for an early working prototype, see <https://forrt.org/replicatethis>). This platform will provide researchers with a moderated, constructive, and impersonal mechanism to nominate specific findings for repetition. It will serve as a centralized starting point for researchers interested in repeatability and act as an alternative metric for research impact by balancing the popularity of nominated research against actual quality criteria (e.g., reproducibility and replicability). The portal will be created in a way that authors of nominated studies will recognize that they have been chosen for relevance. To facilitate meta-research, community-building, and targeted support for replication journals, the portal will include several advanced functionalities:

- Nominations will be tagged to indicate which RJF member journals are interested in publishing the resulting replication report.
- Nominations have to abide by a strict CoC that strongly encourages constructive criticism.
- Authors of nominated articles will be notified so that they can provide guidance and share relevant material if they want or join the project as co-authors.
- Researchers will be able to subscribe to specific nominations to receive updates on discussions, theoretical claims, and subsequent publications.
- Users will have the ability to record formal predictions regarding the outcomes of proposed replications. We will implement algorithms that assign a replicability score to nominations, based on algorithms that are developed as part of the SCORE project and by the FORRT teams (<https://www.cos.io/blog/cos-and-forrt-partner-to-increase-discoverability-and-usability-of-replication-evidence>). Note that as of April 2026, human predictors outperform algorithmic predictions of replication success.
- Prospective replicators will be able to filter replication targets by selecting nominations with high subscriber volumes, controversial theoretical discussions, or inconsistent outcome predictions.
- Interested researchers will be able to tag a nomination as "seeking collaborators," allowing them to team up with international peers to conduct the replication study. Note that a nominated study can be replicated multiple times by independent or overlapping teams.

Risk Management and Contingency Plans

To ensure the uninterrupted success of the project, we have identified potential methodological, technical, and community-related risks and established robust contingency plans. Addressing these proactively guarantees that the project's deliverables will be met even under suboptimal conditions.

Risk 1: Low Engagement from Target Disciplines (WP1 & WP2)

Challenge: The selected underrepresented fields (Marketing, Linguistics, Neuroscience) may exhibit slower adoption rates or lower-than-expected attendance at our capacity-building workshops. *Contingency:* If engagement in a specific discipline is lacking, we will swiftly pivot to adjacent fields that are closer to psychology (e.g., Judgment and Decision Making, Psycholinguistics, and Cognitive Science) where we already possess strong institutional ties and FORRT community support.

- **Linguistics:** Should general linguistics prove difficult to mobilize, we will draw upon our Advisory Board. For example, we are well aware that large parts of general linguistics are not empirical in a way that would make replications and reproductions possible (Le Foll, in press). We will collaborate closely with our Associate Editors for language Elen Le Foll, Lydia Riedl, and Ulrike Gut, and our advisory board member Kevin McManus, all of which are experienced conducting empirical research in linguistics. Moreover, we are already in touch with our partner, the Tromsø Repository of Language and Linguistics (TROLLing), who serve to curate, store, and share data from empirical and replicable studies in linguistics and we are coordinating with colleagues from psycholinguistics and digital humanities (e.g., Karina van Dalen-Oskamp is an R2 Associate Editor, Riva Quiroga has participated in one of our Replication Hub workshops).
- **Marketing:** If broader marketing communities are unresponsive (i.e., we can recruit less than ten participants in the replication workshops), project member Susanne Adler will leverage her dual training to pivot the workshops toward Behavioral Economics and Judgment and Decision Making, fields highly receptive to meta-scientific infrastructure.
- **Neuroscience:** We consider the risk here to be low, as we have already secured strong preliminary commitments. Max Korbmacher is an R2 Associate Editor with expertise in neuroscience and replications, and Janik Golterman, also R2 Associate Editor and expert in neuroscience and replications, has been supervising a project with 60 replications.

Risk 2: Spam and Unconstructive Discourse on the "ReplicateThis" Portal (WP3)

Challenge: Any public-facing academic platform that allows users to nominate the work of others is susceptible to spam, trolling, or an overly combative, personal culture of criticism. *Contingency:* We view the protection of constructive scientific discourse as paramount. To prevent spam and ensure academic accountability, the portal will mandate ORCID Single Sign-On (SSO) authentication for all users making a nomination or leaving a comment. Furthermore, the portal will not operate on a "live-publish" basis. All nominations will enter a moderation queue managed by the *Replication Research*, RJF, and FORRT teams. Nominations will only

be published if they strictly adhere to our established Code of Conduct, which mandates that all justifications for replication be strictly methodological, theoretical, and entirely impersonal.

Risk 3: Low Performance on Quantifiable Success Criteria and Interim Evaluation

As an evidence-based and meta-scientific community, we do not blindly assume the success of our infrastructure. Prior to this grant application, the editorial board of Replication Research transparently preregistered specific success criteria (see OSF Registries: <https://osf.io/kupqt> and <https://zenodo.org/records/19710622>). Rather than acting as a strict "stopping rule" as originally conceived during our unfunded bootstrapping phase, these criteria will now serve as our formal Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for a rigid interim evaluation at Month 24 of this project. The project will be deemed structurally successful if:

1. Usage: At least 12 research articles have been submitted (excluding editorials/internal board majority papers).
2. Efficiency: At least 10 articles have been published, making the journal eligible for immediate DOAJ indexing.
3. Continuity: At least 5 articles are published in the preceding 12 months, indicating sustained community uptake rather than just an initial wave.
4. Resilience: The editorial team consists of at least six active members from at least three different disciplines.

If the live-tracking dashboard (Task 2.1) indicates that we are failing to meet these KPIs by Month 26, we will not dissolve the infrastructure. Instead, the project team will trigger our targeted pivot strategy: We will reallocate resources from WP1 (Workshops) strictly to the disciplines showing the highest initial traction, and we will initiate discussions within the Replication Journal Federation (RJF) to merge editorial workflows (e.g., cascading peer review) with our partner journals to guarantee the long-term preservation and utility of the infrastructure built.

Work programme and proposed methods

Give an account of the steps you are planning to take and describe and justify the methods you will use. List the steps planned for each applicant and draw up a clear overview of the structure and work schedule.

Personnel Structure and Justification

As this is an infrastructure grant (LIS), the requested funds are explicitly allocated to service provision, software development, and community management, rather than academic qualification. The project tasks will be executed by:

- **Principal Investigator** (PI, L. Röseler): Contributing 12 Person-Months (PMs) overall to oversee the project, act as the primary liaison with academic societies and university leadership (WP2), and guide the strategic direction of the journal.
- **Project Coordinator** (PC, Wissenschaftliche:r Mitarbeiter:in, 100%, 36 PMs): A researcher holding a Master's degree or PhD, employed specifically for science management. They will be responsible for organizing the capacity-building workshops (WP1), conducting the systematic policy screening and drafting the policy briefs (WP2), managing the community, and moderating the ReplicateThis portal (WP3 & WP4).
- **Research Software Engineer** (RSE) (Wissenschaftliche:r Mitarbeiter:in, 50%, 18 PMs): An IT specialist (Master/Bachelor level) responsible for the professional technical development of the ReplicateThis portal (WP3 & WP4).

Work Package 1: Provision of Field-Specific Guidance and Capacity Building

This WP focuses on equipping early career researchers (ECRs) with the necessary skills to conduct rigorous replications in currently underrepresented fields (Linguistics, Marketing, and Neuroscience).

- **Task 1.1: Replication Workshops and Hackathons:** We will organize field-specific workshops followed by hackathons. Each event will host up to 30 participants divided into six teams of five. The aim is to enable each team to design and initiate their own reproduction or replication (workshop) and to support them in carrying it out (hackathon and two consecutive mentorship meetings). To maximize impact, we plan to recruit participants from existing DFG Research Training Groups (Graduiererkollegs) and ensure that ECRs are formally rewarded for their time and reach out to conference hosts to suggest featuring the events as pre-conference workshops. The workshop will be structured to meet the standards of the ECTS and, while the formal awarding of credits remains the prerogative of the participants' home institutions, we will provide a certificate of academic workload (workload of 30h per workshop, equating to 1 ECTS credit). This effort will be carried out in collaboration with editors from journals and databases that mandate open data (e.g., the curated linguistics data repository TROLLING with which R2 already has a partnership). **[Personnel Allocation: PI: 2 PMs, PC: 1 PM]**
- **Task 1.2: Structured Mentorship:** To support the successful conclusion of the initiated projects, project members will conduct formal mentoring meetings with the teams one and three months after the initial workshop. Completed reports will be submitted to R2. **[Personnel Allocation: PI: 1 PM, PC: 1 PM]**
- **Task 1.3: Annual On-Site Events:** We will host three annual, multidisciplinary, (2 on-site, 1 online), hackathon-style collaborative events for ECRs (akin to the "Replication Games" like they were conducted in Münster in 2025, <https://indico.uni-muenster.de/e/rg>). These will be organized by the Replication Research (R2) editorial team in cooperation with the Institute for Replication, other replication journals and the local open science community managed by the Münster Center for Open Science. **[Personnel Allocation: PI: 1 PM, PC: 1 PM, FORRT Community: In-kind]**
- **Task 1.4: Long-Term Resource Provision:** Workshop recordings and slides will be published as Open Educational Resources (OERs). Additionally, the workshop facilitators will author deep-dive book chapters guiding researchers in these respective fields, which will be added to a dedicated, openly accessible handbook for reproductions and replications. **[Personnel Allocation: PI: 1 PM, PC: 1 PM]**

Work Package 2: Revision of Promotional Guidelines and Policy Interventions

This WP aims to systematically address and dismantle the formal, institutional barriers that currently hinder repeatability research.

- **Task 2.1: Live Tracking of Replication Rates:**
We will establish a live dashboard to track replication rates for specific journals over time, leveraging the existing FLoRA API. **[Personnel Allocation: RSE: 3 PMs]**
- **Task 2.2: Guideline Inventory and Analysis:**
We will compile an inventory of current promotional and evaluation guidelines across academic societies and institutions. We will systematically screen these guidelines,

specifically the Excellence Strategy of the German federal & state governments in Germany and the Research Excellence Framework in the UK but also doctoral and postdoctoral regulations (Promotionsordnung and Habilitationsordnung), to identify criteria that can hinder engagement with replications, that are outdated regarding journal submission guidelines, or that mandate strictly non-replicative (novelty-only) research.

- **Selection Rule for Universities:** To ensure our analysis targets institutions that disproportionately shape academic norms (e.g., large universities), we will screen the guidelines of the 15 leading research-intensive universities in Germany (German U15) and a sample of 15 top research-intensive universities in the UK (drawn from the Russell Group).

- **Selection Rule for Associations:** We will sample the primary national (UK/GER) and European professional societies for our target fields to which the policy briefs are then addressed. This includes, for example, the European Marketing Academy (EMAC) and Academy of Marketing Science (AMS) for Marketing; the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Sprachwissenschaft (DGfS) and Linguistics Association of Great Britain for Linguistics (LAGB); and the Federation of European Neuroscience Societies (FENS), Neurowissenschaftliche Gesellschaft (NWG), and British Neuroscience Association (BNA) for Neuroscience. **[Personnel Allocation: PC: 3 PMs, PI: 1 PM]**

- **Task 2.3: Policy Recommendations and Dissemination:**

- **Drafting the Brief:** Based on a qualitative content analysis of the screened guidelines, the PC and PI will synthesize the identified barriers into a draft policy brief for university policy makers and academic societies on research assessment in the context of reproduction and replication research. This draft will undergo a consultation phase within the FORRT community, the RJF advisory board, and the Münster Center for Open Science's network which features representatives from 14 departments and different disciplines to ensure the recommendations are practical and discipline-appropriate.

- **Deliverables:** The final output will be a formal Policy Brief outlining necessary systemic changes, accompanied by a standardized "Replication-Friendly Policy Template." This template will provide drop-in legal clauses that faculties can readily adopt to update their regulations to explicitly reward replication research on par with traditional research. Additionally, we will draft specific recommendations for national evaluation bodies (e.g., REF panels, BMFTR) on how to integrate robustness criteria into their assessment frameworks.

- **Dissemination Strategy:** We will actively push these materials to decision-makers through a multi-pronged approach. First, we will conduct direct, personalized mailings of the brief to the Deans and Department Heads of the sampled U15 and Russell Group universities, as well as the executive boards of the sampled academic societies. Second, we will publish the brief as an open-access white paper. Finally, building on my recent firsthand experience and success in leading the University of Münster to sign SF DORA and the Barcelona Declaration, we will launch a highly credible public advocacy campaign at the RJF. This will culminate in a signable open commitment to replications tailored for academic societies and institutions (conceptually modeled after SF DORA and compatible with CoARA). **[Personnel Allocation: PI: 2 PMs, PC: 1 PM]**

Work Package 3: Implementation of the "ReplicateThis" Portal

This WP details the technical development and community rollout of the replication nominations portal.

- Task 3.1: Technical Development: The Project Coordinator, supported by a Research Software Engineer (RSE) with a computer science background, will code the portal based on the existing prototype (<https://forrt.org/replicatethis>). The platform will feature a public-facing page with paper-specific filters and descriptions. **[Personnel Allocation: RSE: 5 PMs, PC: 4 PMs]**
- Task 3.2: Standardized Nominations: The portal will utilize a standardized form allowing users to publicly or anonymously nominate findings for replication. Nominations will require formal justifications (e.g., high theoretical interest, inconsistency with other findings, seminal article status, or high public attention) and recommendations for study type (reproduction vs. replication). Users will also be able to indicate if they are currently attempting a replication or reproduction or if they are seeking collaborators. Moderators will receive emails with nomination texts and buttons to execute moderation actions such as “accept” or “reject” **[Personnel Allocation: PC: 4 PMs, RSE: 2 PMs]**
- Task 3.3: Portal Seeding and Moderation: To ensure immediate utility, the database will be seeded in two ways. First, we will nominate multiple studies per field derived using Isager et al.’s (2025; doi.org/10.15626/MP.2022.3300) citations and sample size logic on the highest rated publications from 2020 – 2022 (years chosen to reflect research that could be cited but that is still recent) out of the five highest ranking journals according to SCImago Journal Rankings (scimagojr.com) SJR values per discipline (*Linguistics and Language* and *Marketing* subject categories and *Neuroscience* subject area). Second, from the chosen journals, we will extract citation-based impact indicators (AttRank) from BIPIScholar’s API and nominate the highest 10 empirical articles per field.
Long-term maintenance and moderation will be managed by R2 and the Replication Journal Federation to ensure nomination texts meet constructive criteria. **[Personnel Allocation: PC: 5 PMs, PI: 1 PM]**
- Task 3.4: Pilot Phase and Community Engagement: We will conduct a pilot phase using test nominations, explicitly soliciting feedback from the authors of the nominated original research. To foster constructive dialogue, original authors will be granted a right-of-reply feature directly on the nomination page. Furthermore, the PC and RA will organize discipline-specific events to discuss seminal, not-yet-replicated findings to generate high-quality nominations. **[Personnel Allocation: PC: 5 PMs, RSE: 1 PM, PI: 1 PM]**

Work Package 4: Integration of Ecosystems

This WP focuses on technically and structurally unifying the newly developed tools with existing institutional and federation-wide infrastructures. By connecting the portal, the journal, and the broader community, this package ensures long-term sustainability, seamless user experiences, and mutual support across the Replication Journal Federation (RJF).

- Task 4.1: Institutional Hosting and Direct Submission Pipeline: We will transition the ReplicateThis portal from a standalone prototype to being fully integrated into the

secure and sustainable website infrastructure of the University of Münster.

[Personnel Allocation: RSE: 2 PMs, PC: 4 PMs]

- Task 4.2: Implementation of an RJF Mentoring Program: To support researchers who choose to take up the challenge of conducting nominated replications, we will integrate a streamlined application system for a dedicated mentoring program. Managed by the RJF, this system will connect prospective replicators with experienced meta-scientists and field experts who can provide methodological guidance throughout the replication process. **[Personnel Allocation: PC: 3 PMs, PI: 1 PM]**
- Task 4.3: Aesthetic Overhaul and Shared Design Guidelines: We will conduct a comprehensive, one-time aesthetic overhaul of the Replication Research website to improve user navigation and professionalize its appearance. As part of this process, we will develop and distribute shared design guidelines, including adaptable, matching CSS templates that can be uploaded to the OJS and that can be easily and optionally adopted by other RJF member journals to establish a cohesive and recognizable visual identity across the entire federation. **[Personnel Allocation: RSE: 2 PMs, PC: 1 PM]**
- Task 4.4: Inter-Journal Reproducibility Workflows via CODECHECK: We will formalize and integrate the existing Replication Research (R2) reproducibility checks into the independent CODECHECK infrastructure with support from its co-founder and maintainer Dr. Stephen Eglen. By establishing this as a standardized RJF workflow, participating journals and their respective research communities will be systematically equipped to share resources and cross-support one another in verifying computational reproducibility prior to publication. We will provide guidelines for authors (e.g., preparation of code and data) as well as documentation for editors of other journals who want to conduct reproducibility checks via CODECHECK as well. **[Personnel Allocation: PC: 2 PMs, RSE: 1 PM, PI: 1 PM]**
- Task 4.5: Implementation of Machine-Readable Publishing Formats (JATS XML & HTML): To fully comply with the technical principles of cOAlition S and the DIAMAS/DOAS standards, we will upgrade the Replication Research publishing pipeline to move beyond PDF-only publication. The Research Software Engineer (RSE) and SHK C will implement automated or semi-automated workflows (e.g., using tools like Texture, Grobid, or OJS XML parsing plugins) to convert accepted manuscripts into standard JATS XML and responsive HTML. This critical infrastructure upgrade ensures maximum findability, and enables robust Text and Data Mining (TDM) for meta-science researchers, vastly improves accessibility for visually impaired readers. **[Personnel Allocation: RSE: 2 PMs, SHK C: 12 months]**

Relevance of sex, gender and/or diversity in the research project

Diamond open access and replication infrastructures can reduce inequities in reading and publishing by removing APCs, but without explicit measures they can reproduce biases in participation, visibility, and topic selection. Our activities (journal operations, guidance development, workshops, nominations portal) therefore embed sex/gender and broader diversity considerations as quality, ethics, and inclusion requirements. At our journal, we require a social responsibility section that requires authors to contextualize the work and discuss groups that may potentially be harmed. We also provide lay summaries of articles that are proposed by handling editors and refined by the R2 Science Communication Manager that we have appointed in April, 2026.

3 Project- and subject-related list of publications

Works cited from chapters 1 and 2, both by the applicant and by third parties. Please include DOI/URL if available. A maximum of ten of your own works cited may be **highlighted**; font at least Arial 9 pt.

- Aczel, B., Szaszi, B., Clelland, H. T., Kovacs, M., Holzmeister, F., Van Ravenzwaaij, D., ... & Gerdal, D. (2026). Investigating the analytical robustness of the social and behavioural sciences. *Nature*, 652(8108), 135–142. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-09844-9>
- Ankel-Peters, J., Fiala, N., & Neubauer, F. (2023). Do economists replicate? *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 212, 219–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jebo.2023.05.009>
- Bakker, M., van Dijk, A., & Wicherts, J. M. (2012). The Rules of the Game Called Psychological Science. *Perspectives on Psychological Science: A Journal of the Association for Psychological Science*, 7(6), 543–554. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691612459060>
- Brandt, M. J., IJzerman, H., Dijksterhuis, A., Farach, F. J., Geller, J., Giner-Sorolla, R., Grange, J. A., Perugini, M., Spies, J. R., & van 't Veer, A. (2014). The Replication Recipe: What makes for a convincing replication? *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 50, 217–224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesp.2013.10.005>
- Brembs, B., Huneman, P., Schönbrodt, F., Nilsson, G., Susi, T., Siems, R., Perakakis, P., Trachana, V., Ma, L., & Rodriguez-Cuadrado, S. (2023). Replacing academic journals. *Royal Society Open Science*, 10(7). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.230206>
- Camerer, C. F., Dreber, A., Holzmeister, F., Ho, T.-H., Huber, J., Johannesson, M., Kirchler, M., Nave, G., Nosek, B. A., Pfeiffer, T., Altmejd, A., Buttrick, N., Chan, T., Chen, Y., Forsell, E., Gampa, A., Heikensten, E., Hummer, L., Imai, T., ... Wu, H. (2018). Evaluating the replicability of social science experiments in *Nature* and *Science* between 2010 and 2015. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 2(9), 637–644. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-018-0399-z>
- Doyen, S., Klein, O., Pichon, C.-L., & Cleeremans, A. (2012). Behavioral priming: It's all in the mind, but whose mind? *PloS One*, 7(1), e29081. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0029081>

- Glöckner, A., Gollwitzer, M., Hahn, L., Lange, J., Sassenberg, K., & Unkelbach, C. (2024). Quality, replicability, and transparency in research in social psychology: Implementation of recommendations in Germany. *Social Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1864-9335/a000548>
- Hardwicke, T. E., Szűcs, D., Thibault, R. T., Crüwell, S., Van Den Akker, O. R., Nuijten, M. B., & Ioannidis, J. P. A. (2021). Citation Patterns Following a Strongly Contradictory Replication Result: Four Case Studies From Psychology. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*, 4(3), 25152459211040837. <https://doi.org/10.1177/25152459211040837>
- Hartmann, H., Azevedo, F., Röseler, L., Wallrich, L., Aldoh, A., Elsherif, M. M., Liu, M., O'Mahoney, R., Pavlović, Z., Reason, R., Skvortsova, A., Agostini, V., Aitchison, L., Al-Hoorie, A. H., Albayrak, N., Ammann, N., Anvari, F., Arriaga, P., Baker, B. J., ... Leech, G. (2026). Tracking and mainstreaming replications in the social, cognitive, and behavioral sciences. *MetaArXiv*. https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/ad2w6_v3
- Lakens, D., Leach, N. M., Haans, A., Uygun Tunç, D., & Tunç, M. N. (2026, April 30). How to analyze a replication study. https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/7ydgq_v1
- Le Foll, E. (in press). Well, parts of linguistics is open": Insights into Linguists' Diverse Understandings of Open Science. *The Journal of Electronic Publishing*. <https://doi.org/10.3998/jep.7974>
- Makel, M. C., Plucker, J. A., Freeman, J., Lombardi, A., Simonsen, B., & Coyne, M. (2016). Replication of special education research: Necessary but far too rare. *Remedial and Special Education*, 37(4), 205–212. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0741932516646083>
- Open Science Collaboration. (2015). Psychology: Estimating the reproducibility of psychological science. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 349(6251), aac4716. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aac4716>
- Reed, W. R., Röseler, L., Saam, M., & Wallrich, L. (2026). No room at the inn? The case for dedicated replication journals. *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Economics*, 120, 102502. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socec.2025.102502>
- Röseler, L., & Röseler, J. (2026). Guess the replication [Computer game]. Retrieved from <https://lukasroeseler.github.io/GuessTheReplication/>
- Röseler, L., Kaiser, L., Doetsch, C. A., Klett, N., Seida, C., Schütz, A., Aczel, B., Adelina, N., Agostini, V., Alarie, S., Albayarak-Aydemir, N., AlDoh, A., Al-Hoorie, A. H., Azevedo, F., Baker, B. J., Barth, C. L., Beitner, J., Brick, C., Brohmer, H., ... Zhang, Y. (2024). The Replication Database: Documenting the Replicability of Psychological Science. <https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/me2ub>
- Röseler, L., Moser, V., Schüller, S., & Förster, C. (2025, Mai 22). Replication Research Symposium: Book of Abstracts. Replication Research Symposium (R2S), Münster, Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15487804>
- Röseler, L., Wallrich, L., & Azevedo, F. (2025). Conditions under which R2 will be discontinued after a runtime of 26 months. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17206100>
- Röseler, L., Wallrich, L., Adler, S., Oppong Boakye, P., Evans, T. R., Goltermann, J., Haven, T., Horstmann, J., Korbmacher, M., Müller, M., Verheyen, S., Visser, I., & Azevedo, F. (2025). A Community Model for Rigorous and Inclusive Scholarship. *Replication Research*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.17879/REPLICATIONRESEARCH-2025-9022>
- Röseler, L., Wallrich, L., Hartmann, H., Altegoer, L., Boyce, V., Field, S., Goltermann, J., Hüffmeier, J., Pennington, C., Pittelkow, M.-M., Silverstein, P., van Ravenzwaaij, D., & Azevedo, F. (2025). Handbook for Reproduction and Replication Studies (Version 0.1). *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.16990114>
- Tyner, A.H., Abatayo, A.L., Daley, M. et al. Investigating the replicability of the social and behavioural sciences. *Nature* 652, 143–150 (2026). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-10078-y>
- Wallrich, L., Röseler, L., Hartmann, H., Ashcroft-Jones, S., Doetsch, C., Kaiser, L., & Azevedo, F. (2026). FORRT Library of Replication Attempts (FLoRA) [Dataset]. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/9R62X>
- Wallrich, L., Tondlekar, R., Röseler, L., Weinerova, J., Baldoni, C., Fouilloux, A., Meier, M., Flores Kanter, P. E., Trajano, I., Vaidis, D. C., Müller, M., Arriaga, P., & Coulson, H. D. (2026). Zotero replication checker: Privacy-first plugin to discover replications from the FORRT Library of Replication Attempts (FLoRA) [Computer software]. https://forrt.org/flora_zotero/

4 Supplementary information on the project context

Section 4 et seq. must not exceed 10 pages.

General ethical aspects

The project builds and operates scholarly publishing infrastructure and conducts meta-scientific analyses; it does not itself collect new human or animal research data. We commit to the DFG Code of Conduct for good scientific practice and adhere to guidelines of scientific publishing as laid out by COS, ICMJE, and COPE (see also our constitution, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17279413>). No support will be sought from the national service centre for Diamond Open Access for the implementation of the activities listed in the work programme, either currently or during the project period.

Research integrity and publication ethics

- R2 requires authors to disclose ethical approvals (or legal bases) for underlying studies, informed consent procedures where applicable, and data protection safeguards. All submissions undergo checks for plagiarism, citation of retractions, citation of studies for which there are replication or reproduction attempts, potential social impact, and conflicts of interest (see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18229852>); COPE workflows guide corrections, expressions of concern, and retractions.
- Open peer review is governed by a code of conduct (civility, evidence-based critique, no evaluation based on outcomes, no discrimination/harassment). Reviewer pseudonymization is available to mitigate power imbalances; editors enforce COI adherence and document decisions openly to ensure accountability and editorial independence from funders or institutions (see <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17241396>).
- Social Responsibility review screens for risks of harm (e.g., stigmatization, misuse), requiring mitigation and contextualization in the manuscript; persistent concerns can lead to rejection.

Nominations portal ethics

- The portal is moderated; nominations must focus on methodological/public value criteria and non-personal language. Defamation, allegations of misconduct, or discriminatory/harassing content are prohibited; suspected misconduct is redirected to institutional channels. Nominators may appear publicly or remain private; portal texts are licensed openly with clear consent.
- We will audit nominations for systemic bias (e.g., disproportionate focus on specific groups or regions; see FORRT's Code of Conduct, <https://forrt.org/coc>) and publish de-identified, aggregate reports.

Intellectual property and licensing

- All project outputs use open licenses (e.g., CC BY for texts, MIT for code and software); third-party content is included only with rights clearance or lawful exceptions; long-term archiving complies with legal deposit. We confirm that source code for the software developed under the project is documented in accordance with the principles of open source and made available for use by third parties.

Considerations on aspects of ecological sustainability in the planning and implementation of the project

The project consists of digital infrastructure: diamond open access only (no print runs or physical distribution), lightweight web delivery, and reuse of existing university hosting. Governance is remote by default, and all training events are hybrid; when travel is necessary, we apply a rail-first policy, select venues reachable by public transport, and keep events low-impact (digital materials, minimal waste, predominantly plant-based catering). Publishing workflows emphasize accessible, optimized formats and discourage unnecessary data or media bloat, while avoiding duplicate storage.

Measures to meet funding requirements and handle project results

Details relating to the requirements stated in the relevant programme guidelines or call text under section I.2.2 (“Proposal requirements and funding conditions”), particularly with regard to handling results and data achieved within the project (measures for storage, long-term provision and dissemination)

We commit to all programme requirements. Publications resulting from the project and any relevant documentation will be available via open access, making them widely accessible for use by third parties. The source code for the software developed under the project is documented in accordance with the principles of open source and made available for use by third parties. Articles will be published under CC BY and software under OSI-approved licenses (e.g., MIT/Apache-2.0) or the respective license required by the associated software such as LaTeX Project Public License. Open peer reviews and reproducibility reports (e.g., CODECHECK certificates) are routinely published with DOIs in the R2 Zenodo community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/r2/records>) and linked to the article record.

Findability and standards compliance are ensured as follows: each article receives a DOI via DataCite and PDF; metadata expose ORCID iDs (authors/reviewers), Funder Registry IDs and grant numbers, CRediT roles, license and data availability statements, and relation types to datasets/code. R2 is indexed in Google Scholar and we will apply to DOAJ after meeting eligibility (expected no later than 01/2028). All metadata are dedicated to the public domain (CC0) consistent with the Barcelona Declaration’s recommendations.

Long-term provision and storage: The University and State Library of Münster (part of the University of Münster) manages the OJS instance that is hosted by the Hochschulbibliothekszentrum in Cologne (HBZ), manages DOI registration, and deposits publications with the German National Library for legal deposit and long-term archiving. OJS is integrated with preservation services (e.g., PKP PN). For supplementary research artifacts, authors are required to deposit data and code in trusted repositories (discipline-specific where possible, in our partner repository TROLLING [<https://site.uit.no/trolling/about>] if a submission comes from linguistics; otherwise Zenodo/Dataverse/OSF) with DataCite DOIs, open licenses, and citation metadata. When legal/ethical constraints prevent public data sharing, authors must provide documented justifications, share to editors/reproducibility staff for verification, and, where feasible, deposit under controlled access; the respective article will include a detailed access statement.

Rights and governance: Authors retain copyright and license their works under the above open licenses; reviewers retain copyright in their reviews and license them CC BY. The journal title belongs to the Münster Center for Open Science (MüCOS) and the Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training (FORRT) and the domain is held by the University of Münster. Editorial and governance documents are published on Zenodo under CC BY to ensure transferability to other contexts. We are fully aligning with cOAlition S technical requirements and the DIAMAS standard. During the project, we will permanently implement the publication of all full texts in standardized JATS XML and HTML formats alongside PDF, dedicating all metadata to the public domain (CC0) consistent with the Barcelona Declaration's recommendations.

Data management and protection: Operational data (editorial workflow, portal submissions, event registrations) are processed GDPR-compliantly with data minimization, purpose limitation, documented retention/deletion schedules, and access controls.

Dissemination: Results will be communicated via the journal site, the Münster Center for Open Science's network, at conferences (e.g., Meta Science Conference, Perspectives on Scientific Error Workshop, and the planned 2027 FORRT conference), the FORRT community of over 1.5K researchers, workshops, open educational resources, and replication and reproduction findings are entered into the FORRT Library of Reproduction and Replication Attempts (FLoRA), which is openly licensed and accessible via an API including a landing page (<https://forrt.org/flora-replication-atlas>). Findings from FLoRA are used in adjacent projects such as the Replication Checker Zotero Plugin (https://forrt.org/flora_zotero), the FLoRA-Notify bot that alerts authors of preprints who cited replicated studies without their replications, and there is a FLoRA-module in the independently developed and maintained Metacheck project (<https://www.scienceverse.org/metacheck/index.html>) that is used by academic journals to check submissions and considered by preprint repositories such as PsyArxiv for inclusion in their standard moderation procedures. Annual reports will summarize outputs. These measures ensure maximum openness, interoperability, long-term availability, and reusability of all project results.

1.1 Formal assurances

Formal assurance must be given that specific conditions of funding will be met. These depend on the funding programme and can include long-term provision of project results, compliance with specifically named standards, or the amount of the applicants' own financial contributions (see "Proposal structure" in the relevant programme guidelines or call text).

In accordance with the funding guidelines for Infrastructures for Scholarly Publishing, we formally confirm and assure the following:

1. Publications resulting from the project and any relevant documentation will be available via open access, making them widely accessible for use by third parties.
2. The source code for the software developed under the project is documented in accordance with the principles of open source and made available for use by third parties.
3. No support will be sought from the national service centre for Diamond Open Access for the implementation of the activities listed in the work programme, either currently or during the project period.

Additional Project-Specific Assurances:

Furthermore, regarding the quality assurance and long-term sustainability of the established infrastructure, we assure that:

- We will formally apply for the indexing of Replication Research in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) as soon as the formal eligibility criteria (e.g., time since launch, number of published articles) are met (expected no later than January 2028).
- The journal's operations and workflows will strictly comply with the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) developed by DIAMAS.
- The long-term archival of all publications from Replication Research and the permanent hosting of the OJS platform are structurally and financially guaranteed via the university's cooperation with the Hochschulbibliothekszentrum (HBZ).

5 People/collaborations/funding

Employment status information

For each applicant, state the last name, first name, and employment status (including duration of contract and funding body, if on a fixed-term contract).

- Röseler, Lukas, Postdoctoral position (permanent contract)

Composition of the project group

List only those individuals who will work on the project but will not be paid out of the project funds. State each person's name, academic title, employment status, and type of funding.

Röseler, Dr. phil, Postdoctoral position (permanent contract)

Institutions or researchers in Germany with which/whom you have agreed to cooperate on this project

- Elen Le Foll, R2 Associate Editor for Linguistics
- Janik Goltermann, R2 Associate Editor for Neuroscience
- Susanne Adler, R2 Associate Editor for Marketing
- RJF members: Marianne Saam (JOPD)

Institutions or researchers abroad with which/whom you have agreed to cooperate on this project

- Lukas Wallrich, R2 Senior Editor and Co-Founder
- Flavio Azevedo, R2 Senior Editor and Co-Founder
- Thomas Rhys Evans (JOPD)
- Stephen Eglen, Maintainer and Co-founder of CODECHECK
- Etienne B. Roesch (ReScience C, ReScience X)

Institutions and researchers with which/whom you have collaborated scientifically within the past three years

This information will help avoid potential conflicts of interest.

- Lukas Wallrich (Birkbeck School of London, UK)
- Flavio Azevedo (University of Utrecht, NL)
- Edzer Pebesma (University of Münster, Germany)

- Elen Le Foll (University of Cologne, Germany)
- Rachel Heyard (University of Zürich, Switzerland)
- Janik Goltermann (Department of Psychiatry and Neuroscience, Campus Benjamin Franklin, Charité–Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Berlin, Germany)
- Lydia Riedl (Marburg University, Germany)
- Max Korbmacher (Haukeland University Hospital, Norway)
- Steven Verheyen (Erasmus University Rotterdam, Netherlands)
- Susanne Adler (Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Germany)
- Thomas Rhys Evans (University of Greenwich, UK)
- Ulrike Gut (University of Münster, Germany)
- Ingmar Visser (University of Amsterdam, Netherlands)
- Jan Horstmann (University of Hamburg, Germany)
- Tamarinde Haven (Tilburg University, Netherlands)
- Moin Syed (University of Minnesota, USA)
- Sebastian Kurten (University of Utrecht, Germany)
- Karina van Dalen-Oskam (University of Amsterdam, Netherlands)
- Nicolas P. Rougier (Université de Bordeaux, France)
- Alexandra Sarafoglou (University of Amsterdam, Netherlands)
- Gilad Feldman (University of Hong Kong, HK)
- Robert Körner (University of Bamberg, Germany)
- Astrid Schütz (University of Bamberg, Germany)
- Bob Reed (University of Canterbury, New Zealand)
- Tobias Rebholz (Duke, USA)
- Julia Gross (University of Mannheim, Germany)
- Jelena Hoghe (University of Bamberg)
- Frank Papenmeier (University of Tübingen, Germany)
- Heidi Seibold (NA, Germany)
- Priya Silverstein (University of Coimbra, Portugal)
- Crystal N. Steltenpohl (COS, USA)
- David Vaidis (Université de Toulouse, France)
- Maike Richter (Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Germany)
- Lisa DeBruine (University of Glasgow)
- Daniel Lakens (Eindhoven University of Technology)
- René Bekkers (University of Amsterdam)
- Marianne Saam (ZBW, University of Hamburg)
- Riva Quiroga (OpenLifeSci)
- Kudakwashe Siziva (Crossref)
- Priti Chahal (semanticClimate)

Project-relevant cooperation with commercial enterprises

If applicable, please note the EU guidelines on state aid or contact your research institution in this regard.

Does not apply.

Project-relevant participation in commercial enterprises

Information on connections between the project and the production branch of the enterprise

Does not apply.

Other submissions

List any funding proposals for this project and/or major instrumentation previously submitted to a third party.

Does not apply.

1.2 Financial contributions

State how much funding and what equipment and staff will be contributed to the project by the applicant(s) (see item "Financial contributions" of the relevant programme guidelines or call)

The applicant institution (University of Münster / Münster Center for Open Science) provides the following in-kind and financial contributions to ensure the long-term operation of Replication Research and the project infrastructure:

Personnel (Baseline Funding):

- **Journal Manager:** A permanent 50% FTE position (TV-L E13) dedicated to journal management, editorial workflow coordination, and RJF secretariat duties. This position is funded through the MüCOS annual budget and covers core editorial operations beyond the project period.
- **Student Assistant:** Funding for a 4-hour/week Student Assistant (SHK) to support editorial operations and community management. This position is covered by the MüCOS annual budget.

Operational Costs:

- **DOI Registration & Crossref:** Annual fees for DOI registration and Crossref metadata services.
- **Publication Costs:** Costs for open access book publication (e.g., chapter processing fees) covered by the MüCOS institutional budget.

6 Requested modules/funds

Explain each item for each applicant (stating last name, first name).

Structure according to the corresponding programme guidelines or call text.

Requested modules/funds

Requested DFG modules

- **Basismodul** (DFG 52.01): personnel, travel, services under "Sonstiges," project-internal publication funds.
- **Projektspezifische Workshops** (DFG 52.06): on-site and online training events.

Personnel (Basismodul)

As this is an infrastructure grant (LIS), the requested funds are explicitly allocated to service provision, software development, and community management, rather than academic qualification. We request funding for standard scientific and technical staff (Wissenschaftliche Mitarbeiter*innen).

Project Coordinator (Wissenschaftliche*r Mitarbeiter*in)

- **Role:** Lead the development and moderation of the Replication Nominations Portal; conduct the systematic policy screening (WP2); coordinate field-specific guidance outputs (WP1); and manage the Replication Journal Federation network.
- **Qualification profile:** The ideal candidate holds a PhD in meta-science, psychology, or a related field (justifying the requested Postdoc-level funding). They must possess

a profound understanding of the open science landscape, excellent science communication skills, and experience in science management or policy. This high level of academic seniority is strictly required to successfully engage in discussions with university leadership (Deans of U15 universities) and executive boards of academic societies during the policy interventions (WP2).

- **FTE/duration:** 100% FTE (TV-L E13 Level 3 to E 14 Level 2), months 1–36.
- **Budget:** 3 * 88,200.00 € = 264,600.00 €

Research Software Engineer (Wissenschaftliche*r Mitarbeiter*in)

- **Role:** Professional technical development of the ReplicateThis portal, API development for the replication-rate dashboard, OJS integrations, CSS/front-end work for the journal, and documentation.
- **Qualification profile:** The ideal candidate holds a Master’s degree in Computer Science, Data Science, Digital Humanities, or a related technical field. They require proven expertise in professional web development, alongside a strong familiarity with open-source publishing systems (particularly Open Journal Systems, OJS) and machine-readable markup languages (JATS XML).
- **FTE/duration:** 50% FTE (Other research assistant), months 1–36].
- **Budget:** 67,200.00 € / 2 * 3 = 100,800.00 €

Student Assistants (Studentische Hilfskräfte mit Bachelorabschluss - SHK)

- **SHK A:** 9 h/week, 36 months; Reproducibility workflow support (embedding checks into the CODECHECK ecosystem, execution pipelines).
- **SHK B:** 9 h/week, 24 months; Organization support; preparation of OERs, formatting of field-specific guidance materials, and workshop logistics.
- **SHK C:** 9 h/week, 12 months; Content migration, conversion of publications to JATS XML, and accessibility testing.
- **Budget:** Based on the institutional hourly rates of the University of Münster 9,167.63 € per year for 9 h/week for student assistants (“Hilfskraftkosten SHB mit Bachelorabschluss; hourly wage of 15,20€ and expenses of 19,52€), 55,005.78 €

Travel (Basismodul)

Purpose: Active presentation of project results at two major international conferences (the Metascience 2027 conference and the World Conference on Research Integrity 2028/2029) and three national/European discipline-specific congresses (one for each target field: Linguistics, Marketing, Neuroscience) to facilitate networking and community uptake.

Budget Breakdown (Total: 5,368 €):

The requested budget covers travel for the PI and/or Project Coordinator to attend a total of 5 conferences over the 36-month funding period. Costs are estimated based on current average rates for academic conferences and standard university travel regulations:

1. International Conferences (2 Events; e.g., Metascience, WCRI)

Estimated duration: 4 days / 4 nights per event (Total for 2 events = 8 days)

- Conference Fees (Kongressgebühren): 2 events × 400 € = 800 €
- Travel Costs (Fahrtkosten): 2 round trips (rail/economy flight) × 350 € = 700 €
- Accommodation (Übernachungskosten): 8 nights × 140 € = 1120 €
- Per Diem (Tagegeld): 8 days × 24 € (standard domestic/EU rate) = 192 €

- Subtotal International: 2,812 €

2. National/European Discipline-Specific Congresses (3 Events; e.g., DGfS, VHB, NWG)

Estimated duration: 3 days / 2 nights per event (Total for 3 events = 9 days)

- Conference Fees (Kongressgebühren): 3 events × 400 € = 1200 €
- Travel Costs (Fahrtkosten): 3 round trips (rail/BahnCard) × 100 € = 300 €
- Accommodation (Übernachungskosten): 6 nights × 140 € = 840 €
- Per Diem (Tagegeld): 9 days × 24 € (standard domestic rate) = 216 €
- Subtotal National: 2,556 €

Total sum: 5,368 €

Workshops (Module Projektspezifische Workshops, DFG 52.06)

- Online Training Events: Two online, half-day training workshops focusing on conducting and reporting replications (no additional costs requested).
- Annual On-Site Hackathons: Three annual on-site "Replication-Games-style" workshops for early career researchers (ECRs), co-hosted with the R2 editorial team and partners. For each of the three events, we plan for exactly 30 participating ECRs and up to 3 invited methodological experts, resulting in 33 external attendees per event.
- Subsidy Character: The requested DFG funds act strictly as a subsidy to the overall costs of these events. The University of Münster (via MüCOS) covers the substantial baseline costs, including venue rentals, technical infrastructure, organizational staff hours (e.g., via additional MüCOS student research assistants), and basic administrative support. The DFG subsidy is requested exclusively to cover the travel, accommodation, and catering costs for the 33 external attendees to remove financial barriers, thereby ensuring high accessibility and diversity among ECRs.
- Budget: 34,500 € in total (approx. 10,000 € travel/accommodation and 1,500 € catering per event). Breakdown: For each of the three hackathons, this will cover 200 € travel costs, 80 € accommodation per night for 33 participants, and 2,260 € as a subsidy towards catering for the two-day hackathon (additional costs will be covered by the Münster Center for Open Science).

Project-internal publication funds (Basismodul 2.6)

- Open access book publication costs will be covered by the Münster Center for Open Science.
- Research articles describing the project outcomes will be submitted solely to diamond open access journals such as Nordic Perspectives on Open Science, Linguistics, Liber Quarterly, European Journal of Management and Business Economics, and o-bib. That is, publications resulting from the project and any relevant documentation will be available via open access, making them widely accessible for use by third parties.